

ENHANCING LEARNER TRANSFORMATION THROUGH HOLISTIC QUALITY EDUCATION BY INTEGRATING EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE IN CURRICULUM IN LEARNING INSTITUTIONS IN KENYA

Harriet Wambui Njui¹

Abstract:

Since the coining of the term emotional intelligence (EI) in the late 1990s by Goleman with a claim that emotional intelligence is more important than IQ, educators and researchers have realized the need to develop students' emotional intelligence (EI), and this has increased interest in studying the concept in relation to its impact on education. EI is considered to be one of the key components of emotional adjustment, personal well-being, life success, and interpersonal relationships in different contexts of everyday life. However, although research supports the relevance of EI to indicators for personal and school success such as interpersonal relationships, academic achievement, and personal and social adjustment, the findings on promoting EI in schools have been inconsistent. In addition, education across the globe has until the end of the 20th century emphasised intellectual and academic aspects of students and neglected emotional and social aspects. The 21st century education emphasizes the need to develop students with skills that enhance their personal and professional skills. Developing students with these components could transform them into empowered ethical citizens who are capable of contributing to the welfare of the society. This study reviews literature on EI with a view to making recommendations on how learning institutions in Kenya could integrate EI in the curriculum in order to enhance students' emotional health and well-being, academic achievement, and other adaptive outcomes.

Keywords: transformative education, emotional intelligence, 21st century education

1. Introduction

Goleman defines emotional intelligence (EI) as *"the capacity for recognizing our own feelings and those of others, for motivating ourselves, and for managing emotions well in ourselves and in our relationships."* He also asserts that EI is responsible for 67 percent of those abilities leaders need for superior performance and is twice as important as their

¹ Correspondence: email harrietwnjui@gmail.com

IQ or technical experience (Hamilton, 2017). Elias defines EI as *“the set of abilities that helps us get along in life with other people in all kinds of life situations”* and emphasizes the need for educators to understand that teaching EI is a process that takes years before teachers and students can reap its benefits. Hamilton (2017) observes that our EI is our ability to identify our emotions, as well as others’ emotions, and to learn to use those emotions to improve our communication skills, meet challenges, deal with conflict, and control our emotions in a positive way that leads to success. EI also enables students to cope with serious stress, anxiety, and depression that can lead to violence, drug use, and other problems associated with today’s dynamic society. The benefits of the abilities accorded by EI calls for educators to nurture students with the skills to enable them make adjustments in order to cope with the numerous challenges of the global society. They also enhance individual students’ personal and professional development.

This notwithstanding, Cohen observes that while a growing number of school programmes include elements of instruction aimed at a child's emotional needs, too many of those programmes are fragmented, short-term, and not well-integrated into the regular curriculum or school structure. (Emotional Intelligence is the Missing Piece, 2001). Clear structures of EI programmes in learning institutions should be established to enhance effective development of EI skills among students.

Busch and Oakley (2017) emphasize that EI capacities and abilities should be developed on a lifelong basis from the early years of learning to the highest level because each developmental stage has specific needs and experiences that require educators, parents, community and education stakeholders to collaborate in order to mould learners’ values and habits in the context of their age. In agreement, Tustin (2017) observes that laying a good foundation of EI at preschool ensures that students enter primary and secondary school equipped with EI skills and this safeguards pre-teens and teens from engaging in risky behaviours such as drug and substance abuse. It is also likely to help them have self-confidence and make safer choices.

In addition, teens who are well equipped with EI skills are likely to cascade the same behaviours to universities and other tertiary institutions they are admitted to. Busch & Oakley (2017) also observe that developing EI skills in the formative years provides the foundation for future habits later on in life. On the contrary, however, schools in Kenya tend to focus more on intellectual development from very early years of schooling. This has led to neglecting the development of other key aspects of education that enhance one’s social and emotional development including values and attitudes (Wamahiu, 2015). The researcher attributes the rampant corruption, impunity and negative behaviour and destruction by the youth in Kenya to lack of values education in school and society.

Notably, teaching EI has become a necessary task in the educational arena and most parents and teachers consider mastery of these skills a priority in the socio-emotional and personal development of children. However, teaching EI skills requires using programmes which explicitly include and highlight emotional skills based on the ability to perceive, understand and regulate emotions. It also requires giving priority to practice, training and improvement to allow students opportunity to exercise and

practice emotional skills in order to adapt them within their individual natural repertoire (Berrocal & Ruiz, 2008). Effectiveness of EI training programmes is supported by research (Lopes & Salovey, 2004; Maurer & Brackett, 2004), despite the fact that the studies are scanty. Learning institutions in Kenya should borrow from such research evidences in order to come up with systematic programmes for teaching EI skills. They should also be cognizant of the fact that effective teaching of social and emotional learning programmes requires collaboration among parents, teachers, policy makers, and other stakeholders in education. It further demands that schools facilitate parents, teachers, staff and administrators with training on ways of promoting behavior that improves EI skills such as communication, empathy, self-awareness, decision-making, and problem-solving (Emotional Intelligence is the Missing Piece, 2001).

As noted above, the EI skills should be taught at all levels of learning. This requires teachers to develop innovative, effective and best practices for teaching EI to different categories of people. For instance, effective teaching of EI in preschools requires teachers and families to collaborate on the interactions and learning activities to involve children in at both school and home. At secondary school level, the teaching of EI should prepare students for the transition to young adulthood and college through counselling, involving them in social work and by ensuring that the curriculum focuses on preparing them emotionally for the challenges of navigating adolescence. This entails that the curriculum develops students' self- and social awareness, critical thinking, effective decision-making, creative problem-solving ability, and goal-setting skills. Leaders should also be trained on how to integrate EI practices into their everyday lives and to increase their awareness of their own and others' emotions and learn about how emotions influence decisions (Teaching Emotional Intelligence- Yale Center for Emotional Intelligence).

However, Scott (2015) asserts that most learning institutions across the globe seem not to be developing students with EI skills because they prefer using the transmission model of education which is basically confined to cognitive development. This is despite the fact that technological development has rendered the model obsolete. Evans (2002) and Fernández-Berrocal & Ramos (2002) confirm this and also note that the necessary emotional and social competencies for coping adequately with negative, destructive emotions generated by teachers and parents towards students who are weak academically have not been explicitly taught in schools and the community because up to until the end of the 20th century, education has focused on intellectual development, under the conviction that students' emotional and social aspects of education belong to the private sphere, where each individual is responsible for his/her own personal development. This narrow approach to education cannot meet the needs of the society. The 21st century has brought a new view of the diverse reality of human functioning that has created awareness of the need for families, schools and society to explicitly address the education of emotional and social aspects. Learning institutions in Kenya should embrace this paradigm shift to align with the 21st century education landscape.

Interestingly, postmodern societies in the first world want not only to be wealthy, opulent and among the top 25 countries in Gross Domestic Product (GDP), they are also looking for a new values hierarchy and a new way to relate to objects and time, to ourselves and to other persons, in order to find individual happiness. The societies for instance seek for their citizens' satisfaction in life, in their realization of the painful paradox for one to live in an opulent society which covers one's physical and material needs, but does not make one happy (Lipovetsky, 2006). In agreement, Berrocal & Ruiz (2008) point out that there is no linear association between children's welfare in a country, and its Gross Domestic Product (GDP): the wealth of societies does not guarantee its citizens' satisfaction and happiness. This implies that without EI, there is something missing to make one complete, regardless of one's socio-economic status.

2. Aspects of Emotional Intelligence (EI)

Busch & Oakley (2017) outline five areas of focus in EI: relationship skills/active listening, self-awareness, empathy, managing emotions, and self-regulation.

Active listening creates two-way communication which involves following dialogue and responding to others using body language and being able to demonstrate understanding by verbally summarising back key messages that have been received. This enhances good communication with others which becomes a gateway to better learning, friendships, academic success and employment.

Self-awareness means "*knowing one's internal states, preference, resources and intuitions.*" Developing students' self-awareness enhances their well-being because self-aware people tend to act consciously rather than react passively, to be in good psychological health and to have a positive outlook on life. They also have greater depth of life experience and are likely to be more compassionate to themselves and others (Goleman, 2017). Research by Green Peak Partners and Cornell University examining 72 executives at public and private companies shows that self-awareness is a crucial trait of successful business leaders; "*a high self-awareness score was the strongest predictor of overall success*" (What is Self-awareness and Why does it Matter?, 2017). Busch & Oakley (2017) also observe that people with low self-awareness are at risk of not realising how they come across to others and letting an over inflated self-image skew their behaviour and social interactions. Further, research has established that teaching metacognitive strategies helps students improve their self-awareness (Busch & Oakley, 2017). These findings shows the need for learning institutions in to establish systematic EI curricula programmes in order to make interventions for students with low self-awareness or deficient in other EI skills to enhance their success in life and good behaviour image.

Empathy is the ability to take the perspective of another person while being non-judgemental, recognising the emotions they are feeling, and being able to convey their perspective back to them. Reflecting back the other person's perspective helps to make the other person feel understood, and this increases the likelihood of collaboration and support (Busch & Oakley, 2017). The authors also emphasize that adults and those in

administrative responsibilities in a school set up should play the role of a model in order help learners internalize the habits and values taught. This, they say, is crucial as children develop empathy through observing how others show it. Hamilton (2017) also observes that teaching empathy to students requires teachers to model empathy in their relationships with students and members of the school community and to make it a rule that everyone in the classroom is expected to show respect for their classmates to enhance empathy and good relationships among students. Cohen observes that self-awareness and empathy play a huge role in every aspect of life and notes that how people feel about themselves and others can affect their ability to concentrate, to remember, to think, and to express themselves. He also points out that children without emotional intelligence do not follow directions, continually go off-task, cannot pay attention, and have difficulty working cooperatively. Developing students with EI skills could alleviate such undesirable attributes.

Managing Emotions is the ability to take charge of ones emotions rather than the emotions taking charge of one. It means choosing the right way to respond to emotions to create a space to reference one's commitments and values (How to Manage Emotions/Psychology today). Bariso (2016) outlines seven tools for managing emotions namely pause-taking, volume control, tuning dial, mute-letting, record, playback and fast forward.

Pause refers to taking a moment to stop and think before acting or speaking, especially in a situation where emotions run high while *volume control* is the ability to recognize your emotions are getting out of hand, and to dial things back. This requires training oneself to recognize when volume is starting to go up. *Tuning dial* means *tuning in* to the other person and listening carefully to truly understand their problem instead of focusing on what to say next while *mute* means avoiding sharing your point of view and letting the other person if she/he is in a highly emotional state. *Record-* while on mute entails focusing on mentally recording key points the person is willing to share to help you learn more about their perspective as a foundation for finding solutions at a more appropriate time. *Playback* refers to revisiting the topic after both parties have had time to cool down. This requires giving thought to the ideal location and time for calm and rational discussion. *Fast forward* entails forgetting about how you feel in the moment and thinking about the effects of your actions in a month, a year, five years etc. *Fast forward* can help one achieve clarity of mind and make sound decisions particularly when emotion is clouding one's judgment. Acquiring these tools is a process that requires learning institutions to be deliberate in establishing systematic structures for teaching EI skills to students. Developing students with these tools is crucial because, as Bariso (2016) observes, learning to control emotions is critical in enhancing students' holistic wellbeing in both school and the society.

Self-regulation is behaviourally defined as the ability to act in one's long-term best interest, consistent with one's deepest values and also notes that violation of the values causes guilt, shame, and anxiety, which undermine wellbeing. On the other hand emotionally, self-regulation is the ability to calm oneself down when upset and cheer

oneself up when down (Stosny, 2011). Further, Stosny observes that emotions are driven by three motivations namely approach, avoid and attack.

Approach motivation entails wanting to get more of something, experience more, discover more, learn more, or appreciate more. Examples of approach emotions are interest, enjoyment, compassion, trust, and love while its behaviours include learning, encouraging, relating, negotiating, cooperating, pleasing, delighting, influencing, guiding, setting limits and protecting. On the other hand, *avoid* motivation, leads one to getting away from something. This means lowering its value or worthiness of attention. Avoid behaviours include ignoring, rejecting, withdrawing, looking down on and dismissing. *Attack* motivation leads one to wanting to devalue, insult, criticize, undermine, harm, coerce, dominate, incapacitate, or destroy. Its emotions are anger, hatred, contempt, and disgust while its behaviours are demanding, manipulating, dominating, coercing, threatening, bullying, harming, and abusing. Students should be helped to understand these drivers of motivation and their behavioural and emotional implications through EI teaching programmes in school. This could enable them to successfully work out self-regulation of their emotions and behaviour in order to act in a positive manner.

Hamilton (2017) identifies other EI skills namely seeking opinion, problem-solving, building character and incorporating humour in the classroom. Each skill is briefly described below.

Seeking opinions entails giving students the opportunity to share their ideas and opinions and this encourages them to come up with ideas for classroom activities and also motivates them to learn and to feel more able to tackle projects on their own. Further, students learn to listen to their classmates, respect the opinions and ideas of others, and this enhances their EI. However, these skills demand a paradigm shift in pedagogy from knowledge transmission to collaborative pedagogy to train students to exchange ideas. Providing opportunities for students to share ideas and respond appropriately can also help them to become better listeners and life-long learners.

Problem Solving. The Concise Oxford Dictionary (1995) defines a problem as a doubtful or difficult matter requiring a solution and something hard to understand or accomplish or deal with. Effective problem solving involves working through a systematic process of identifying the problem, structuring the problem, looking for possible solutions, making decisions, implementing solutions, monitoring/seeking feedback (Problem Solving Skills/Skills You /Need). The processes are briefly explained below.

Identifying the problem involves detecting and recognising that there is a problem; identifying the nature of the problem and defining the problem. *Structuring the problem* involves observation, careful inspection, fact-finding and developing a clear picture of the problem to gain more information about it and increase understanding. *Looking for possible solutions* requires generating a range of possible courses of action through a brain-storming session on possible solutions or part solutions. *Making a decision* involves careful analysis of the different possible courses of action and then selecting the best solution for implementation. However, some solutions may not be possible,

due to other problems, like time constraints or budgets. *Implementation* involves accepting and carrying out the chosen course of action or acting on the chosen solution. *Monitoring/seeking feedback* involves reviewing the outcomes of problem solving over a period of time, including seeking feedback on the success of the outcomes of the chosen solution (Problem Solving Skills/Skills You /Need). Effective problem solving requires that these steps are followed systematically

Learning institutions should develop students with problem-solving skills because problem-solving is a universal job skill that applies to any position and every industry. The skill gives students a distinct edge in employment as employers look for new job entrants who have demonstrated problem-solving skills (Career Builder, 2017).

Building Character is crucial in enhancing an individual's set of psychological characteristics that affect the one's ability and inclination to function morally, and this leads a person to do or not to do the right thing (Berkowitz). Hamilton (2017) suggests that character could be developed through reading assignments of personalities who display good character and also notes that a discussion of the assignment can lead to students' understanding of the importance of trust, honesty, and responsibility shown by the characters. These values could help them become dependable and successful adults with high IE. Building teacher capacity in approaches to teaching EI is crucial to effective implementation of EI programmes in both classroom learning and in other activities outside the classroom.

Incorporating humour in the Classroom is also beneficial to students. Research indicates that playing a game, telling a joke, or laughing with students can calm nerves and put things back into perspective when a problem has grown out of proportion. It also diffuses conflict and relieves stress. However, teachers should ensure that humour is never at the expense of one of the students. They should also avoid sarcasm as it can corrode trust with students.

Developing students with a high EI is crucial as it helps them to maintain their good physical and mental health, learn how to communicate with others, and achieve success in their future careers (Hamilton, 2017). Incorporating EI in the curriculum is imperative if learning institutions in Kenya are to promote holistic education that is aligned to the 21st century curriculum which is based on knowledge, skills, character and metacognition (The 21st Century Education-Center for Curriculum Redesign, 2016).

UNESCO's four pillars of education also require education to develop a complete person who has cognitive tools required to better comprehend the world and its complexities, and to provide an appropriate and adequate foundation for future learning; skills that enable individuals to effectively participate in the global economy and society; self-analytical and social skills to enable individuals to develop to their fullest potential psycho-socially, affectively as well as physically, for an all-round 'complete person; and values implicit within human rights, democratic principles, intercultural understanding and respect and peace at all levels of society and human relationships to enable individuals and societies to live in peace and harmony by resolving and managing conflicts (The Four Pillars of Learning/Education/UNESCO). Further, education is expected to adapt to change and embrace lifelong learning.

Learning institutions in Kenya should integrate EI in the curriculum in order to align with these demands of education. To enhance the development of the EI skills, the institutions should establish learner support services including mentoring and coaching, guidance and counselling, academic guidance and advisory, clubs and societies, and sports and games.

2.1 Enhancing EI Skills through Mentoring and Coaching

Mentoring and coaching benefit students in various aspects including increasing reflectivity and clarity of thinking; improving psychological wellbeing and confidence; enhancing better problem-solving skills including decision-making; enhancing practitioner knowledge and skills; improving sharing of practice; achieving better communication and relationships; enhancing more positive attitudes towards professional and career development, and improving self-management and self-learning skills. Further, mentoring and coaching enhance personal effectiveness and ability to work smarter; development of techniques for constructively challenging unhelpful behaviours such as negativity and limiting beliefs; enhance energy and job satisfaction; and increased personal productivity. In addition, mentoring and coaching promotes development of skills of citizenship such as integrity, patriotism and fairness (The Impact of Mentoring and Coaching). These skills resonate well with EI skills. However, it is not certain that public universities in Kenya have time to mentor and coach students given the huge student-teacher ratios and shortage of teaching staff (British Council Report, 2012). This implies that students do not get an opportunity to hone their EI and other soft skills that have become so crucial in today's job market.

2.2 Enhancing EI Skills through Guidance and Counselling

Guidance and counselling (G&C) service caters for students' social and emotional needs to help them adjust to the school environment and also respond to emerging challenges in the society. The service is aimed at assisting students to understand themselves, others, school environment and acquire abilities to adjust accordingly. For instance, when students are admitted into a university, they are purely on their own (independent) and in most cases away from their parents. G & C services are necessary to help them adjust to their new environment and develop the attitude to set individual goals that will enhance improvement of their educational programmes. It also helps them to learn to set individual goals that enhance improvement of their academic performance; preparing them for unanticipated life events and ongoing personal difficulties and challenges faced in and out of the school (Cooper, 2007).

However, despite its significant benefits, Michubu, Nyerere & Kyalo (2017) report that availability of quality guidance and counselling service in universities in Kenya is low. Gudo, Olel and Oanda (2011) support the report noting that majority of the students (56%) in public universities are dissatisfied with guidance and counselling services. The finding is paradoxical because the Association of University and College Counsellors survey (2002) cited by Michubu, Nyerere & Kyalo (2017) indicates that all public universities in Kenya had established a guidance and counselling department in

their campuses. This implies that universities have guidance and counselling departments in place but they do not offer quality services. Providing vibrant guidance and counselling services in learning institutions is critical in enhancing development of EI skills among students. Notably also, policy documents including Inter-University Council for East Africa (2010) and Commission for University Education Guidelines (2014) have outlined the need for learner support services in universities as prerequisites for creating quality environments to enhance quality learning.

2.3 Enhancing EI Skills through Academic Guidance and Advisory

Academic guidance and advisory entails assigning a number of students to a teacher who assists them to make advancement towards their objectives and targets on individual basis. This enables individual students to exploit their potential according to their ability, interest and talent. It also helps them to make decisions regarding their career aspirations and to address the challenges they may face in their academic life. Students are also helped to position themselves for core-curricula activities and leadership, and to also develop social skills to build positive relationships with teachers, counsellors, and outsiders. This is made possible by teaching them the core elements of relationship building and how to stand out within a community; and teaching them stress management and social development-helping them build skills to surround themselves with good influences (Student Mentorship Programme/College Vine). However, it is uncertain that public institutions in Kenya, particularly universities are able to establish effective academic guidance and advisory structures, given the high student- teacher ratios they deal with as noted above. Reforms are critical if learning institutions are to provide this support service to enhance students' transformation through integrating EI skills in the curriculum.

2.4 Enhancing EI Skills through Clubs and Societies

Clubs and societies offer students activities designed for fun, mutual trust and friendship among them. They also enhance their academic experience beyond the classroom. Participation in clubs and societies further enhances development of students' leadership skills, discipline, sharing, respect; positive attitude towards life and people; teamwork; negotiation; acceptance of different kinds of people (culture, colour, ability and religion); empathy and fair play. The skills resonate well with EI skills. However, while primary and secondary schools in Kenya provide students with opportunities to join clubs and societies of their interest, most schools use the time allotted for clubs and societies to prepare students for national examinations as explained below. This implies that the students confine themselves to academics and end up not developing the skills.

2.5 Enhancing EI Skills through Sports and Games

Sports and games provide students with a variety of character-building experiences such as how to cooperate with others and play fairly; enhancing development of learners' self-discipline as they strive to learn and excel at a sport (which could be

transferred to academics and improve school performance); and enhancing critical-thinking and problem-solving skills. Participation in sports also makes learners stay healthy and strong. For instance, running releases negative anxiety and tension, and this enables students to concentrate in school. In addition, physical benefits impact on learners' emotional well-being, which, in turn could improve school performance. These skills compare well with EI skills. However, to help students realize these benefits, learning institutions should promote sports and games and require participation by every student (National Association for Sport and Physical Education, 2013). However, the high premium given to examination and certification in Kenya has compromised students' participation in sports and games. For instance, primary and secondary schools use the time allotted to student activities and learner support services to prepare students for national examinations (Njui, 2010, Wamahiu, 2015). This means the students are denied opportunities to hone their EI skills. A paradigm shift in education from emphasis of examination and certification to acquisition of skills is imperative if students are to reap the benefit of the learner support services discussed above.

2.6 Enhancing EI Skills through curricula reforms

Reforms in curricula and teaching approaches are crucial in enhancing EI. For instance, a shift from transmission to collaborative teaching pedagogies enhances development of 21st century graduate employability skills such as commitment, problem-solving and adaptability and also benefit both individual and collective knowledge growth (Hampson, Patton and Shanks, 2011). Further, the approaches help students to develop other skills including ability to work in teams, solve complex problems, and knowledge transfer to address challenges in different circumstances (Darling-Hammond, 2008).

However, collaboration does not just happen; Barron and Darling-Hammond (2008) maintain that students should be taught team building skills to help them learn to collaborate, negotiate and contribute to joint assignments and experience the sharing of roles, responsibilities and ownership of learning. Collaborative learning also enhances the development of metacognition, improvement in formulating ideas and higher levels of discussion and debate, as well as teaching learners to monitor each other, detect errors and learn how to correct their mistakes (Laal et al., 2013 & Trilling and Fadel, 2009). It is imperative that learning institutions in Kenya embrace the reforms if they are to equip students with relevant skills that can help them confront the complex challenges of the dynamic global society.

In line with the view, Sessional Paper No. 2 of 2015, informed by Kenya Constitution 2010 and Vision 2030 recommends reforms in education and training in Kenya which are aimed at human and economic development. It also recommends that education provides for the development of the individual learner's potential in a holistic and integrated manner in order to produce balanced citizens. Further, the paper recommends a competency based curriculum; establishment of a national learning assessment system, early identification and nurturing of talents, as well as introduction and integration of national values and national cohesion into the curriculum. Realizing

these recommendations could enhance students' EI as the skills outlined resonate well with EI skills. Interdisciplinary education should also be embraced as it enhances deeper understanding of subject matter and this helps to develop students with 21st Century skills including problem-solving, critical thinking, communication and collaboration which also align well with EI skills. However, effective enhancement of EI skills requires a learning institution to establish clear EI programmes and the specific learner activities in and out of the classroom that will enhance the development of various skills.

3. Research Findings on EI and Implications

Tustin (2017) observes that there is a strong correlation between students' emotional intelligence and their classroom performance and also notes that students with low emotional intelligence may struggle to focus and have relationships with their peers or may even show aggression. She further asserts that students with lower emotional intelligence tend to struggle to communicate their feelings with their peers, and this can result in struggling to form friendships with classmates or even relationships with adults. They are also aggressive because they do not have the skills to communicate or manage their emotions appropriately. Tustin (2017) emphasizes the need to develop EI skills from preschool through all other levels to curb such behaviour problems and their negative impacts on learning. This is crucial because research shows that students who participate in EI instructional programmes exhibit less aggressive behaviour towards adults and their peers. Developing EI also improves classroom environment, and this enhances effective teaching and learning. A study which tracked high-IQ students from childhood to late adulthood found that those who achieved notable adult career success showed greater *"will power, perseverance and desire to excel"*. These characteristics are also linked to better school grades, earnings and job satisfaction (Busch and Oakley, 2017). The findings indicate that EI has a significant positive impact in the academic life of students as well as their employment.

Mayer & Salovey (1997) also found that overall emotional intelligence, emotional perception, and emotional regulation uniquely explained individual cognitive-based performance over and beyond the level attributable to general intelligence. However, research also shows that the successful schooling of EI is still undetermined as little objective evidence attesting to the useful role of EI as a predictor of school success and adjustment exists beyond that predicted by intelligence and personality factors. Thus, more expansive research in EI and academic debates among educators and stakeholders in education are needed to address crucial issues prior to developing and implementing EI programmes (Zeidner, Roberts and Mathews, 2010). These research findings seem to contradict the effective role of EI in enhancing performance, communication, social and emotional wellbeing of students. More research is needed to verify the findings.

Carmeli and Josman (2009) assert that individuals who are high in emotional intelligence are likely to exhibit a higher level of work performance outcomes. Similarly, Schutte et al.'s (1998) self-report measure of EI shows positive relationships between

emotional intelligence and employees' work outcomes. However, the authors maintain that the correlation requires further research to establish the connection between emotional intelligence and work outcomes. In agreement, Jordan and Troth (2009) state that although the potential links between emotional intelligence and performance continue to garner interest, few empirical studies have examined this phenomenon. They also note that influence of EI on team performance is of particular interest to researchers and practitioners as teamwork becomes more prevalent in organizations today. Despite the scarcity of research in the correlation between EI and performance, literature review in this area has illustrated significant benefits of EI skills in enhancing students' success in many aspects of life that convinces the author to believe that EI has the potential to impact academic and work performance.

Schutte et al (2010) examined the link between EI and interpersonal relations in seven studies. The participants with higher scores for emotional intelligence in the first 2 studies had higher scores for empathic perspective taking and self-monitoring in social situations while participants in the third study with higher scores for emotional intelligence had higher scores for social skills. Participants in the fourth study with higher scores for emotional intelligence displayed more cooperative responses toward partners while those in the fifth study with higher scores for emotional intelligence had higher scores for close and affectionate relationships. In the sixth study, the participants' scores for marital satisfaction were higher when they rated their marital partners higher for EI while seventh study participants anticipated greater satisfaction in relationships with partners described as having EI. Also, in six studies involving a total of 603 participants, Malouf, Schutte & Torsteinsson (2013) established a significant association ($r = .32$) between EI trait and romantic relationship satisfaction. The association between the EI of an individual and his or her self-reported romantic relationship satisfaction was significant, as was the relationship between an individual's EI and the partner's level of satisfaction with the relationship.

The researchers note that the association between EI trait and romantic relationship satisfaction requires intervention studies aimed at increasing EI in couples in order to increase romantic relationship satisfaction. These findings indicate that EI has an impact on individuals' holistic well-being-physical, emotional and social. They also provide enough evidence that EI has the potential to develop students with the personal and professional skills needed for success in life and employment. Learning institutions should put in place structures that enhance development of students' EI in order to exploit the benefits of the above attributes of EI. A policy on integration of EI in the curriculum is necessary to ensure that learning institutions implement it. In addition, ongoing teacher capacity building on effective ways of developing students with EI skills is critical if adequate development of the skills is to be achieved.

Further, research indicates that EI plays a basic role in establishing, maintaining and having quality interpersonal relationships. For instance, emotionally intelligent persons are skilful in perceiving, understanding and managing their own emotions, and they are also able to extrapolate these skills to the emotions of others (Brackett et al., 2006; Extremera & Fernández-Berrocal, 2004; Lopes, Salovey, Cote, Beers, 2005).

Learning institutions in Kenya should exploit these benefits of EI to enable them facilitate a balanced education that is capable of developing the various compartments of the whole person-cognitive, psychomotor, social and affective.

Additionally, studies in the United States show that university students with higher EI report fewer physical symptoms, less social anxiety and depression, greater use of active coping strategies for problem solving, and less rumination. These findings show that EI skills enhance one's personality and this eventually translates into success in life and workplace. It is crucial that EI is integrated in the curriculum in universities to strengthen what has already been taught at lower levels in order to enhance curriculum continuity in EI. Developing students with EI could also provide interventions for the numerous social and emotional challenges affecting universities and other levels of learning in Kenya including rape, pornography, truancy, drug and substance abuse. Also, the ability to pay attention to emotions, experience feelings with clarity and be able to recover from negative states of mind influences students' mental health and also affects academic performance. Persons with limited emotional skills are more likely to experience stress and emotional difficulties during their studies, and consequently will benefit more from the use of adaptive emotional skills that allow them to cope with these difficulties. It is crucial that students are empowered with EI skills as they may act as a moderator of the effects of cognitive skills on academic performance (Fernández-Berrocal, Extremera & Ramos, 2003; Gil-Olarte, Palomera & Brackett, 2006; Pérez & Castejón, 2007; Petrides, Frederickson & Furnham, 2004).

On the other hand, gaps in EI skills affect students both inside and outside the school context (Mestre & Fernández-Berrocal, 2007; Sánchez-Núñez, Fernández-Berrocal, Montañés & Latorre, 2008). For instance, students with low levels of EI show greater levels of impulsiveness and poorer interpersonal and social skills which encourage the development of antisocial behaviours (Extremera & Fernández-Berrocal, 2002; 2004; Mestre, Guil, Lopes, Salovey & Gil-Olarte, 2006; Petrides et al., 2004). Researchers also suggest that people with lower emotional intelligence are more involved in self-destructive behaviors such as tobacco consumption (Brackett & Mayer, 2003; Brackett, Mayer & Warner, 2004; Canto, Fernández-Berrocal, Guerrero & Extremera, 2005; Trinidad & Johnson, 2002; Trinidad, Unger, Chou & Johnson, 2004a; Trinidad, Unger, Chou & Johnson, 2004b; Trinidad, Unger, Chou & Johnson, 2005). To the contrary, adolescents with ability to manage their emotions are more able to cope with them in their daily life, facilitating better psychological adjustment, and so they present less risk for substance abuse. Specifically, adolescents with a wider repertoire of affective competencies based on the understanding, management and regulation of their own emotions do not require other types of external regulators such as tobacco, alcohol and illegal drugs to recover from negative states of mind provoked by the wide range of stressful life events which they are exposed to at this age (Ruiz-Aranda, Fernández-Berrocal, Cabello & Extremera, 2006).

In summary, research provides evidence that the problems affecting youth are caused by emotional and social risk factors, and the best way to prevent these problems would be through practical development of children's social and emotional skills in a

positive, stimulating atmosphere (Greenberg et al., 2003; Weissberg & O'Brien, 2004). Developing students with EI skills could also provide intervention for those who are already indulged.

4. Conclusion

As noted in this study, problems affecting the youth in learning institutions in Kenya are caused by emotional and social risk factors. These problems could be prevented through lifelong development of students' social and emotional skills in a positive, stimulating atmosphere in school, home and community. However, development of these skills should be a conscious and collaborative effort of teachers, staff, administrators, parents, education stakeholders and the community. EI skills should be emphasized at all levels of learning starting from preschool to give children a head start in EI during their formative years. This makes it easier to nurture the skills at higher levels of learning as the children would cascade positive moral and social attributes to each subsequent level of learning. Effective development of the skills requires learning institutions to ensure that EI programmes have well established structures that enhance proper implementation in the context of the learner. Learning institutions should also have a policy on integration of EI in the curriculum to ensure that it is taught. They should also entrench total quality culture to ensure that all sections of the institution and the people involved model the habits and values taught to enhance internalization of the same by students. The home and community environment(s) should also positively enhance the development of EI.

5. Recommendations

The following recommendations are made with specific reference to learning institutions in Kenya.

5.1 Emphasize Holistic Development of Students

Learning institutions should shift education focus from academic emphasis to skill development to ensure that curriculum offers a balanced education with knowledge, skills, character and metacognition to help students maintain good physical and mental health, learn how to communicate with others, and achieve success in their future careers.

5.2 Build Teacher Capacity on EI skills

Learning institutions should provide teachers with ongoing professional development on skills and facets of EI and their usefulness in enhancing learners' social relationships and academic performance.

5.3 Emphasize the Need to Model the Teaching of EI Skills

Teachers, staff, administrators and parents should internalize the fact the fact that the effective way of teaching students EI skills is by modelling.

5.4 Devise Innovative Approaches to Teaching Emotional Intelligence

Learning Institutions should collaborate with likeminded institutions and education stakeholders to developing innovative, effective approaches to teaching emotional intelligence to students of various ages, staff, parents, teachers, and administrators.

5.5 Establish Structures for integrating EI in the curriculum at various levels of learning with a Policy

The government should provide a policy for EI in the curriculum and establish the structures needed to systematically implement it. Curriculum programmes should also reflect the various aspects of EI in their course content to ensure that the skills are implemented.

5.6 Embrace reforms in curricula and teaching Methods

Learning institutions should employ collaborative teaching methods and interdisciplinary education to enable them develop learners with EI skills and habits such as self-efficacy, empathy, conflict resolution, problem-solving, critical thinking, communication, collaboration patience and accommodation of individual differences. They should also individualize and personalize instruction and assessment in order to meet the needs of individual learners with a view to enhancing a feeling of belonging to all.

5.7 Provide learner support services

All learning institutions should provide students with learner support services including clubs and societies, sports and games, academic advisory, guidance and counselling, and mentorship and coaching to enhance development of EI skills outlined above.

5.8 Strengthen school-home relationships

Learning institutions should build strong school-home relationships to enhance the teaching of EI. Leaders should also be trained on how to integrate EI practices into their everyday lives and to increase their awareness of their own and others' emotions and learn how emotions influence decisions.

5.9 Embrace Lifelong Development of EI

Development of EI should be a continuous process from preschool to university. This ensures that students are provided with the skills needed to cope with the dynamic society.

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